

Studies in Vitamin C. Part II. The Vitamin C Contents of the Liver and Muscle of some Indian Fresh-water Fish.

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It has been shown by the author (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 701) in a previous communication of this series that of all the parts of an animal generally used for edible purpose, the liver is the richest and the muscle the poorest in vitamin C, although considering all the tissues, the liver is not the organ richest in vitamin C. The concentration of the vitamin in the suprarenal cortex is greater than its concentration in the liver. However, on account of the very minute size of the suprarenal in proportion to the liver, the latter is a greater source of the vitamin. In the present investigation the vitamin C contents of the liver and muscle of some Indian freshwater fish have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The material was freed from all adhering tissues and bones as far as possible, and pressed between filter papers. 5-10 G. or as much of this as could be available were used in the determination of the vitamin. The vitamin C content was estimated by titration with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol after extracting with trichloroacetic acid as described in the previous communication.

The relative vitamin C values of the liver and muscle of different fish are given in Table I. The concentration of trichloroacetic acid in the final filtrate containing the vitamin, in our case, is about 5%. McHenry and Graham (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 2013) points out that 5% trichloroacetic acid has a destructive effect on vitamin C. We have found that the vitamin is destroyed slowly but in about half an hour the destruction of the vitamin is not so appreciable as to warrant the prohibition of 5% concentration of trichloroacetic acid in the final filtrate. In most cases the extraction of the vitamin and its titration are over in half an hour. The results of some experiments on the vitamin C content of the same extract just after extraction and 30 minutes after extraction are given in Table II. It will be seen that the vitamin C content does not diminish to a great extent after 30

minutes in trichloroacetic acid. Pure ascorbic acid in a solution of 5 % trichloroacetic acid concentration has also been titrated against the indophenol reagent. It has been found that the tritration values immediately after solution and after 15 and 30 minutes are identical.

Glick and Biskind (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 115, 551) found that both the concentration and the amount of vitamin C per cell in bovine adrenal increase with the age of the foetus until the calf stage while the concentration of the vitamin per cell in the adult gland is lower than the concentration of the vitamin in the calf gland. This is in agreement with the result found by us in the case of fish liver and muscle. It has been found that in the bigger fish of the same variety both the liver and the muscle are poorer in vitamin C than the liver and the muscle in the smaller fish. In Table III are given the vitamin C contents of the liver and muscle of fish of different weights of the same variety. These fish, for strict comparison, were collected from the same source. This result also agrees with the findings of Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 30) in the case of fruits. They found that with the gradual increase in the age of the fruit the ascorbic acid content decreased.

TABLE I.

Vitamin C Contents of Liver and Muscle of Different Freshwater Fish. (in mg./100 g.).

Name of fish. Vern. name (Bengali)	Scientific name.	Vit. C. Contents	
		Liver.	Muscle.
Rohit (another sample)	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	160.0 66.5	20.0 6.8
Kalbosh	<i>Labeo calbosi</i>	57.3	11.2
Katla (another sample)	<i>Catla catla</i>	29.6 11.9	7.0 9.2
Mrigal	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	28.5	11.0
Hilsa	<i>Clupea ilisha</i>	48.0	27.7
Air	<i>Artus artus</i>	23.0	11.7
Bacha	<i>Cluptionsoma garua</i>	40.8	11.0
Boal	<i>Wallago attu</i>	16.0	6.0
Dhain	<i>Silonia silundia</i>	114.4	16.3
Pangash	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i>	23.0	12.5
Sharputi	<i>Barbus sarana</i>	58.4	16.4
Bhola	<i>Sclaeana cottor</i>	59.1	14.7

TABLE II.

Vitamin C content of the same extract just after extraction and 30 minutes after extraction having a concentration of 5 % trichloroacetic acid (in mg./100 g.).

Name of material	Vit. C content	
	just after extraction.	30 mins. after extraction.
Liver	66.51	64.71
"	57.28	56.6
"	23.02	22.5

TABLE III.

Vitamin C content of the Liver and Muscle of Fish of different weights of the same variety (in mg./100 g.)

Name of fish.	Wt.	Vitamin C contents	
		Liver.	Muscle.
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	5.0 lbs.	66.51	6.8
"	2.5	160.0	20.0
<i>Catla catla</i>	32.0	29.64	7.0
"	1.2	40.26	8.6
"	0.32	41.9	9.16

DISCUSSION.

A previous observation by the author (*loc. cit.*) about the vitamin C contents in the liver and muscle of animals has been confirmed in the case of freshwater fish obtained locally. The highest content of vitamin C (160 mg./100 g.) has been found in the liver of *rohita* (*Labeo rohita*) while the lowest (16 mg./100 g.) has been found in the liver of *boal* (*Wallago attu*). The highest vitamin C content (27.65 mg./100 g.) of muscle has been found in the case of *Clupea ilisha*, the lowest being in the case of *Wallago attu*. It has also been observed that a concentration of 5 % trichloroacetic acid in the final extract has, for practical purposes, very little destructive effect on the vitamin C content provided the extraction and titration with the indophenol reagent is over in about half an hour. The particular tissues of the younger fish are richer in vitamin C than those of a bigger fish of the same variety.

In conclusion I wish to thank Dr. S. L. Hora of the Zoological Survey of India for kindly supplying me with the scientific names of most of the varieties of fish used in this investigation.